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NaClO₄ ionic strength using Calvin – Bjerrum potentiometric titration technique.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The coumarins and their corresponding diketones were prepared by the method described earlier³. Dioxane was purified⁸. The transition metal ions were used in the form of their nitrates. A Elico LI-120 digital pH meter with an accuracy of ± 0.01 pH unit was used for pH-titrations. The pH correction factor for the non-aqueous medium was applied⁴ and the thermodynamic values reported.

The experimental setup and the method of calculations was the same as described earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

In the present investigation only one dissociation constant was obtained and is assigned to phenolic OH. The accuracy range of proton – ligand constant is ± 0.03 . The difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values of the lanthanide complexes was less than 1.78 log units indicating the simultaneous formation of both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. It was therefore decided to calculate the $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values by employing the method of least-squares⁶ (Table 1). The accuracy range of $\log K$ values is ± 0.05 log units and these values are pertaining only to conditional stability constants for the systems studied.

Plots of $\log \beta$ against pK values of the ligands were linear suggesting identical binding sites in all the ligands.

Studies on Lanthanide Metal Complexes of some Substituted-coumarins and their Corresponding Diketones

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THE present communication forms a part of our investigation of the complex formation between some physiologically active compounds belonging

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Cations	Ligands											
	IC		ID		IIC		IID		IIIC		IIID	
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$										
H ⁺	9.85	—	10.25	—	8.92	—	8.70	—	9.68	—	8.60	—
La ³⁺	6.29	5.51	7.07	7.01	5.52	PPT	5.26	4.42	5.69	5.65	6.74	6.21
Pr ³⁺	6.77	6.14	7.22	7.08	5.76	PPT	5.37	5.16	6.19	5.86	7.30	7.03
Gd ³⁺	7.32	6.48	8.95	7.07	6.99	5.73	8.09	5.92	6.42	6.27	8.79	8.22
Tb ³⁺	7.52	6.31	8.21	7.16	7.49	5.78	7.02	5.31	6.62	6.03	7.61	6.90
Dy ³⁺	7.51	6.60	8.03	7.35	5.96	5.29	5.39	4.10	8.41	5.69	8.61	7.50

to lactone class and transition and lanthanide metal ions, and is in continuation with our earlier work¹. The study deals with the determination of dissociation constants of some substituted-coumarins and their corresponding diketones and stability constants of their lanthanide metal complexes in 50% (v/v) water-dioxane medium at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and 0.1 M

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having cell dimensions $a=9.017 \text{ \AA}$, $c=8.117 \text{ \AA}$, $V=521.70 \text{ \AA}^3$, $\rho=2.3003 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, $n=1$; where (Dan. Van) and (Dan. Sal) stand for phenolic OH deprotonated Schiff bases.

Experimental

The experimental details, elemental analyses, ir spectral data, conductivity values have already been reported in the earlier communication¹. The X-ray data were recorded on a Phillips PW 1050/70 machine attached with a diffractogram. The diffraction pattern was recorded at a chart speed of $2^\circ (2\theta)/\text{min}$ at $5-80^\circ (2\theta)$ using the scale $1^\circ=1 \text{ cm}$.

X-Ray Diffraction Studies of some Thorium(IV) Schiff Base Complexes

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In continuation to our investigation¹ on thorium(IV) complexes with Schiff bases derived from 1,8-diaminonaphthalene (Dan) with vanalline (van) and salicylaldehyde (sal), we report herein the powder X-ray diffraction data for the complex $[\text{Th}(\text{Dan. Van})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ having cell dimensions $a=b=c=6.7011 \text{ \AA}$, $V=300.91 \text{ \AA}^3$, $\rho=4.3258 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, $n=1$, and the complex $[\text{Th}(\text{Dan. Sal})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses of $[\text{Th}(\text{Dan. Van})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ and $[\text{Th}(\text{Dan. Sal})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ correspond to the molecular formulae as $[\text{Th}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ and $[\text{Th}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{NO})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$, respectively. The diffractograms record 7 reflections for the first and 11 reflections for the second compound between 5 and $80^\circ (2\theta)$ with maxima at $2\theta=44.75^\circ$ for the first and $2\theta=23.8^\circ$ for the second which correspond to $d=2.0205 \text{ \AA}$ and $d=3.700 \text{ \AA}$, respectively. The 2θ values for prominent peaks are listed in Table 1. All main peaks have been indexed^{2,3} and their $\sin^2\theta$ values compared with the calculated ones. Comparison of the values reveals a good agreement between the calculated and observed values of $\sin^2\theta$. The unit cell has been calculated by the

TABLE 1—X-RAY DATA OF Th^{IV} COMPLEXES

Peak no.	d	Relative intensity $\times 100 I/I_0$	Observed $\sin^2 \theta$	Calculated $\sin^2 \theta$	(hkl)	2θ
(i) $[\text{Th}(\text{Dan. Van})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$						
1	3.228 5	61.8	0.056 40	0.052 82	200	27.50
2	2.353 3	56.4	0.107 0	0.105 6	220	38.25
3	2.020 5	65.4	0.145 2	0.145 2	311	44.75
4	1.482 2	29.0	0.269 9	0.237 7	420	62.50
5	1.437 1	32.6	0.237 1	0.239 8	332	64.75
6	1.282 5	29.0	0.360 5	0.356 6	333	73.80
7	1.220 9	34.4	0.397 6	0.396 1	521	78.10
(ii) $[\text{Th}(\text{Dan. Sal})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$						
1	5.601	74.4	0.018 3	0.018 45	110	15.55
2	4.650	85.4	0.027 75	0.027 67	111	19.17
3	3.700	100.0	0.042 5	0.042 95	210	23.80
4	2.804	32.10	0.075 15	0.073 79	220	31.90
5	2.657	31.20	0.083 98	0.083 01	300	33.70
6	2.172	26.30	0.125 7	0.123 1	321	41.55
7	2.029	29.00	0.144 0	0.147 6	004	44.60
8	2.003 6	29.00	0.147 7	0.147 6	400	45.20
9	1.729	23.6	0.198	0.198 7	332	52.90
10	1.646	12.8	0.218 9	0.221 4	422	55.80
11	1.538	18.2	0.250 7	0.249 1	511	60.10

For complex-I (cubic system): $a=b=c=6.7011 \text{ \AA}$, $V=309.11 \text{ \AA}^3$, mol. wt.=784, density (ρ) (calcd.)= 4.3258 g cm^{-3} , $n=1$, density (obs.)= 4.3479 g cm^{-3} . For complex-II (tetragonal system): $a=8.017 \text{ \AA}$, $c=8.117 \text{ \AA}$, $V=521.70 \text{ \AA}^3$, mol. wt.=722, density (ρ) (calcd.)= 2.3033 g cm^{-3} , $n=1$, density (obs.)= 2.3275 g cm^{-3} . For cubic system: $a^3 = \frac{\lambda^3 (h^3 + k^3 + l^3)}{4 \sin^2 \theta}$; for tetragonal

system: $\sin^2 \theta = \frac{\lambda^2}{4} \left[\frac{h^2}{a^2} + \frac{k^2}{a^2} + \frac{l^2}{c^2} \right]$.